

→ Parameters for New Religion (PNR 1.0)¹

MESS 0030

Parameterizing the New Religion (PNR) 1.1: the Breath of God and the Three Pure Ones... A miniature comparison of Salvation, Liberation, and Enlightenment as well as the Philosophæther (plasma) of the “Wind/Breath of God” (Qi)

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ABSTRACT

In the previous paper, the author laid out an idea: that mankind, moving forward in time naturally, or through a SPACERS-like planning², would come to create a New Religion that is in a way like the original religion - the true religion: based on plasma-electromagnetism. However, the author wanted to parameterize it with Western humanistic egalitarianism. The author, in this work, makes it clear that there are underlying - non-dogmatic - aspects based on bioelectric, or aetheric, properties called anciently the “breath of God” (Qi, etc.) These three “pure” systems of salvation, liberation, and enlightenment all hinge around this same ‘spiritual technology’ which is very ancient. It is the first true basis for the New Religion.

Keywords: Qi - Ch’i - Prajna - Ka - Ru’ach - Wind of God - Thunderbolts - Messiahs - Tao

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https://www.academia.edu/38206009/Parameterization_of_New_Religion_utilizing_EPEMC_and_Western_Humanistic_Egalitarianism_as_a_guide

² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

Review of the Threefold Sciences³ - the “True Science” aka “True Religion”

This piece has to have regrettably short paragraphs, to stay within the framework. There is already a larger, more comprehensive work, and it's important to reference that text. The issue here is that we want to put forward our best feet in the discussion of an ancient early religion, pre-existing these “Three Pure Ones.” They all lived in the Transition Period, and at the beginning of the Religious Period⁴. They were inheritors, therefore, of the true religion that pre-existed bureaucracy. And therefore, we are interested in the backstory. Also, the distance from here to these men, these philosophers, is less than from then to the ancients. And that is less than from the Sumerians to the Tepe Period! The origins of religion are stooped in many, many thousands and dozens of thousands of years. These men, however, practiced abstruse philosophies and sciences handed down from these far remote times, and they passed on what they understood. All of them were meditators, after a fashion. All of them had roots in mysticism, and all of them were men of grand compassion and righteousness. So, let us briefly describe their prescriptions, and their demonstrations - if not remonstrations - and try to understand things as they would have in their own time. Most importantly, what the Egyptians called “ka” the breath of life, or of God. This is, according to EPEMC⁵, merely internal examples of the cosmic plasma seen in the sky.

Salvation - “Thus Come One” of the Western Continent - the Christ; manifestation of the Chrissus Prophecy

The Son of Heaven is said to come and go, at will, and to manifest in royalty. In the case of the Christ there is a long chain of lineage stretching back to King David (and beyond) to prove the “royal” lineage of Yeshua (Jesus)⁶. The fact cannot be verified. However, we do know the Christ/Chrissus prophecy⁷ long pre-existed the Jews, and probably or possibly went back to the original Egyptians. Who may, or may not have been Sumerians to start.

In the Sutras, a “buddha” of the “western continent” is mentioned who will (as Amditabha) take one to the Pure Land⁸. The interesting correlation is, at this time (and likely forever more) a directly indirect reference. However, we do know one thing. There is only ONE Christ, which is an appellation, not a last name.⁹ And there is no argument that he *is* the Christ (everyone says this, and nothing else). He also was real^{10,11}. Therefore, what B. Graham has said, “What will we do with this man, Jesus?” is eternally poignant. If he was real, as is indicated by Roman soldier testimony, then one simply has to ask oneself where one stands. But it is clear in one regard: no one else has claimed to be the Messiah *and* produced miracles, in front of so many, with so much eyewitness testimony. Therefore, we must see that the messiah, and more importantly his “Comforter” (the Holy Spirit, or “ru’ach”) and the meditations he was clearly teaching the Apostles, and also his ability to perform healing miracles are absolutely key. His powers could even be transferred through common garments of the time, made of either wool and linen or linen and silk... which according to the Chinese the latter are fair

³ MIMS: The threefold Sacred Sciences

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EPEMC
<https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc>

⁶ Matthew 1:1-17

⁷ <https://biblelineministries.org/egypt-in-prophecy/>

⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Buddhism/Pure-Land>

⁹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christ_\(title\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christ_(title))

¹⁰ Is Jesus Historical? What Do The Romans Say About Him?

¹¹ What Did Jesus REALLY Look Like? Ethnicity, Hair, Skin, Eyes, Body Type.

conductors of Qi! As we may see, later, what was transferred - his 'power' - is termed Te¹². Therefore we also expect that that moment, in particular, is indicative that Jesus' glow may have actually been from a type of low-charge aetheric plasma! What alchemical and esoteric sciences was he practicing? There are stories of "rainbow bodies" out of the East¹³. Perhaps these are related.

How the Jews became "chosen" - Electrostatic Lift

To understand Yeshua, one has to understand his people. They lived isolated, and culturally exposed, at the crossroads of the world. It is almost sure that he studied Sufism¹⁴, or Sufi-like practices, which may have come back and forth along the Silk Road¹⁵. And where did the Jews - ancient practitioners of the Qabalah¹⁶ - get the ideas for the Holiest of the Holies¹⁷, and the very idea that they were "Chosen"? Dr. Velikovsky asserts that "rabbinic sources" (unconfirmed) make it clear that the Red Sea was lifted up by the "Lord's" electrostatic force. Jehovah, J'v'ah, Jove... it is Jupiter! Or more clearly, the brief period of time Jupiter was our "star",¹⁸ and more importantly, when Venus was passing near, electrifying the auroras and the mountains. The uplifted sea waters were dropped because of a Thunderbolt, according to Dr. Velikovsky, and killed not only the Egyptian army, but most of the Hebrews¹⁹. And it was the ones who survived this, and the years in the desert... who were chosen. And the kævod²⁰ - the "glory" of the Lord - may have been radioactive material, or merely plasmoids on display... and we have no other way of translating this.

The Sumerian-Hebrew//Ziggurat-Pyramid//Moshe-Tablets 'hypothesis'

It is quite possible, and not totally improbable, that the Hebrews were themselves, already an ancient race. Among all the "ites" mentioned in the Torah, it is curious that the Sumerians are never mentioned. After the rise of Akkad and Babylon, where did these ancient wise people go? Were they conquered and consumed, or wiped out? Is it possible they went west, seeking the other fertile lands? If so, did they build the early pyramids as Ziggurats in a foregone era of colonial expansion²¹, semi-validating the translations of Sitchin²²? And were those structures later turned by a new race, perhaps Atlantians or others that arrived from the west, or the North, into the shapes we now see? There is some strong evidence for this. But more interestingly, what do we see in many places where old empires are supplanted by newcomers? Frequently they do become slaves in their own lands. And when this happens, they devolve - intellectually - and yet retain some of their former beliefs and culture. Could the Hebrews, by the time of Moshe, have devolved so far as to be almost totally illiterate, and would he have to have taught them everything he learned from the Egyptians and their priestly class, to revive them?

Now, suppose that Moses did this, and he took a ravenous, half-destroyed horde of illiterate pseudo-pagans into the wilds of Sinai. And suppose he was inspired to climb the Holy Mountain, looking for the

¹² <https://www.britannica.com/topic/de>

¹³ <https://www.amazon.com/Rainbow-Body-Realization-Tibetan-Tendzin/dp/1583944915>

¹⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Sufism>

¹⁵ <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/issa-on-the-silk-route/articleshow/11252998.cms>

¹⁶ The-Sacred-Magic-of-Abramelin-the-Mage.pdf

¹⁷ https://www.openbible.info/topics/the_holy_of_holies

¹⁸

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

¹⁹ <https://www.amazon.com/Worlds-Collision-Immanuel-Velikovsky/dp/1906833117>

²⁰ Hebrew To English Kabbalah Dictionary.pdf

²¹ How They Moved the 60-Ton Granite Blocks into the Great Pyramid | Ancient Architects

²² <https://www.amazon.com/12th-Planet-Book-First-Chronicles-ebook/dp/B0057GR5ZA>

Lord, and encountered his signs and wonders. Suppose that he meditated and prayed upon these for many days and was in fact guided (MIMSically) as to how to fix this devolved and depraved horde. What would be natural? To place these upon *tablets*, as the Sumerians of old did... the Tablets of Destiny²³. And recording these, what did he find?

The Desecration of the Tablets (tablets of Destiny?) - What the Psalms indicate they were doing in the name of Venus (the golden calf)

The Psalms and Exodus make it clear that various acts of debauchery and depraved behaviors were gotten up to by the Hebrews. Judging from the calf, and the general worship of Ishtar and Innana in those days, and what we know of Venus worship worldwide and from the New World... we can only speculate as to the "abominations" that are mentioned here. Two, in particular: ritual heart sacrifice, and cannibalism. This combined with the worship of a golden calf as an idol "before the Lord" is almost assuredly the real reason for the "trouble" that has followed the Jews - the Chosen people - since the ancient past. Not so much vengeance of God, but hidden shame in documents.

Moses' Lord & the Burning Bush

This *kævod* may be unidentifiable, but the Lord is less problematic. Fortunately, there are connections in ancient Chinese to the Mesopotamian region, and when we look at the Chinese plasmaglyphics²⁴, it is clear that there are three identities of the "Above God:"

1. The fertility Star Lord - ie: Shamash²⁵, and later Saturn then Jupiter
2. The cosmic pole and energy connecting these two lords²⁶; particularly as the Thunderbolt itself.
3. The Plasma-electromagnetic Force; particularly "the One" above the "Great Man", is capable of holding *four* "maltese crosses" under His arms.
 - a. Remember that the Chinese word for "oneself" is "Ge" which means Halberd, and has the trident and alpha 'fish' symbol within it; indicating God was the Force, as well as the three-faced-God (of Jupiter, Saturn, and Neptune, or Enlil, Anu, and Enki, or Is, Ra, and El... as it were)²⁷

So what made the bush glow? Some have said it was hallucinogens²⁸. Others said that he was only meditating; which can produce DMT naturally²⁹. But what if he meditated there *because* of an actual glowing and 'burning' bush? How and why? Plasma has odd behaviors, and if it is upon a mountaintop, which is a bit more electrified, then there is at least a plausibility that the plant was itself glowing with plasma. There are even some cultures - wise cultures - which believe plants of old age, or many roots (like mugwort³⁰), will have a form of consciousness³¹. Consider the remote possibility that the plant even interacted with the plasma-electromagnetism and that it could *lubricate* 'discussions' between God and the wizard, Moshe. It

²³ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tablet_of_Destinies_\(mythic_item\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tablet_of_Destinies_(mythic_item))

²⁴ https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

²⁵ https://www.academia.edu/50912947/The_Dwarf_Star_God_Origins_slideshow

²⁶ See: Egyptian symbol for Ka as a sign of the connection of all of these ideas. Saturn and Jupiter are the right and left hands of God. In Hinduism, they are Rama and Lakshmana (brother archetype).

²⁷ https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

²⁸ <https://www.nbcnews.com/id/wbna23468364>

²⁹ <https://medicine.umich.edu/dept/neurology/news/archive/202102/does-human-brain-make-dmt>

³⁰

http://www.esalq.usp.br/lepse/imgs/conteudo_thumb/Plant-Consciousness---The-Fascinating-Evidence-Showing-Plants-Have-Human-Level-Intelligence--Feelings--Pain-and-More.pdf

³¹ <https://forestmedicine.net/ecological-intelligence-blog/2017/3/21/yarrow-and-the-path-of-the-magician>

sounds implausible... but so does transfer of power-charge (Te) from Jesus through linen, to a woman that grabbed his robe... and he *felt it*.³² Yet, it does appear that this happened and is not even a unique or novel situation in the world of eastern mysticism. Miraculism is commonplace in the Sino-Vedic (and Tibetan) multiverse.

Yeshua of Nazareth, master of Charge and Aether

Jesus didn't ride donkeys backwards, as Laozi, but he would ride into town on the back of a donkey **glowing**. He, and the others, are also routinely depicted with halos around his head, as if *charged up*, with special powers. As we will see later, powers (siddhis³³ सिद्धि) are said to come with a steady increase in connection to the Qi. But also, there is an aspect of cleansing cells, DNA³⁴, etc., and replacing bad karma with good karma. More interestingly, powers come with moral implications - just as Te implies³⁵ - and Jesus is nothing if not **powerful and moral**. Charge and aether appear to be the things that accumulate within the crown, and heart, and lower Dan Tian ("sea of Qi"), and connect one to good L.U.C.K.³⁶ (or fortune, as it were). The Taoist Thunder magicians actually 'consume' this charge during a Thunderstorm, as a final act of acquiring thunder magik powers, right through the Si Shen Cong and Du-20.³⁷

Meanwhile, Jesus appears to have performed a form of zen-like meditation, involving long quiet prayer, which would often make the apostles fall asleep³⁸. It was during these times that the Thus Come One was tempted by the Devil, and shown visions, etc³⁹. Through this process he was able to acquire massive amounts of charge, especially out in the desert away from people and distractions. He could direct this charge to still waters and storms, or cast 'demons' (mental aberrations?) out of people - as the author wants to do with the QiRI device - or to heal people. He was also sharper and smarter than his peers and the rabbi. He was able to alter matter, and later resurrect his own body⁴⁰ (which had not yet rotted⁴¹). How would any of this be possible without Qi: charge and aether? We will look at it more in a bit.

The Aether Flexion Wave as a source of miraculism

If the aether can be bent, flexed, etc.⁴² and moves outwards from a central source (just as the author demonstrated in AFW 1.0)⁴³, perhaps this is the way that material substrata was altered by Jesus and other sages with the Rainbow Body? However, if there is also an invisible materialesque stratum that *overlays* or *underlies* (via the Principles) the entire chemical/AME matrix then would it not also make sense that those who appear to have special powers, are those who can control the AME via charge and the Force. If they can flex the aether, to alter the AME of creation, are these not godlike abilities and powers? If Jesus was doing this, then He is either the Lord - as he claimed (or allowed others to claim) - or he is at least a very unusual and special prophet, and not a common man like others.

³² Matthew 5:25-34 ; note that it is sometimes power, sometimes virtue, and indicates the same work, Te even in the Aramaic and Greek.

³³ Note the word has the "croess" X in the glyph; <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Siddhi>

³⁴ [MIMS 4.31-4.36- The Storage of Karma and Junk DNA](#)

³⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/de>

³⁶ [MIMS 2.1.1 Business & Analytics](#)

³⁷ [Taoist-Thunder-Magic.pdf](#)

³⁸ Mark 14:37

³⁹ Matthew 4:1-11

⁴⁰ Matthew 28:2-7

⁴¹ John 20:20, Luke 24:39-40

⁴² [MESS0017: AFW - Using Fisheye and Pinch lens to discern Pixelation Adaptation](#)

⁴³ [MESS0012: CRH - The Aether Flexion Wave](#)

Mechanism of Pre-birth Reincarnation... the “Resurrection”

Follow this: the rip in the vale, and the **thunderbolt** striking the temple... are all signs of spiritual/aetheric motion⁴⁴. And If the spirit splits from him, is he not likely to feel abandoned? If then this spirit waits until the body is essentially dead (but not truly, if no one knew to check pulse), and then re-enters it and re-animates it... (a miracle he also caused twice already to happen for others with hands-on *and* “spooky action at a distance”) then couldn’t he resurrect? Is it not at least plausible that such a mechanism might exist... in a world that has as many wonders and mysteries as ours?

If this spirit was not himself but His [One]Self, then is not God rebirthing himself, just as the Saturn lord took over for Shamash (making Enki the ‘elder brother’)? If this spiritual power is **Te**⁴⁵, and it can transfer via cloth, couldn’t it also make itself into a plasmoid (as the author has found a ‘ghost’ to be, previously⁴⁶)? If so, it can move along a spiral or move out, and maybe it can move back into a body.

Liberation - “Thus Come One” of the Tao - Laozi (Old Master); manifestation of the Te

If Lao Tzu was Lao Er⁴⁷, and if he really left town on the back of a donkey, then he wrote only two verses (surely), and no more. We know because of the Ma Wang Dui tomb⁴⁸, that the Tao-te-ching used for thousands of years is definitely not a pristine perfect copy.⁴⁹ It was rearranged into an 81-verse version in the Religious Period. Therefore, let us not rely only upon the TTC, but upon *older* texts, such as the “12-Sided Jade Knob”⁵⁰ and the “Nei Yeh.”⁵¹ And these texts make clear that the key to wuwei (無為) is not the intellect/mind. It is the heart-mind (“xin”), a plasmascript that also seems to refer to the four gas giants, as the heart (so to say) of the solar system - of the EDIN⁵². “All Under Heaven” (Tian Xia, 天下) refers to not just China, but the Earth (“Creation”). But collecting the Te, as we will see putting the Qi or ru’ach in the heart, the Sage is born, and the prophet gains real, palpable power.

The Heart-transformer

The heart has electrical fibers, called the Purkinje fibers⁵³, plus all the muscular and nerve endings that come to it and through it. Also, there is an emotional or spiritual heart on the right side, proximal to the liver and gallbladder. If the heart is constantly moving energy, blood, and electricity, then it could be performing as a form of bioelectrical transformer. Perhaps the Anubis myth⁵⁴ is more about keeping the heart light of material and sin (mind guilt-constructs of one's past misdeeds) than of a physical weight measurement at death. And where will we see this behavior? In the psychological manifestations of the prefrontal cortex: the third eye.⁵⁵

⁴⁴ Not unlike lightning striking the mural of George Floyd in the face. The man was Hell-bent and buried in a golden casket.

⁴⁵ Note the taran → D sound transcription as our cultures interact runically.

⁴⁶ MIMS 4.21-22 - White and Black Spaces; MED 2.01

⁴⁷ <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/laozi/#DatAutLao>

⁴⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mawangdui>

⁴⁹ <https://www.barnesandnoble.com/mobile/w/lao-tzus-tao-te-ching-lao-tzu/1124123541?ean=9780231118170>

⁵⁰ The 12 Sided Jade Knob

⁵¹ <https://www.amazon.com/Original-Tao-Foundations-Mysticism-Translations/dp/0231115652>

⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Garden_of_Eden

⁵³ <https://www.britannica.com/science/Purkinje-fiber>

⁵⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Anubis>

⁵⁵ <https://consciousreminder.com/2017/04/12/scientific-basis-spiritual-concept-third-eye/>

The Golden Light or Flower

The Taoist texts make the assertion that a cleared channel, and a clear conscience, enables the golden light of the heart region (middle Dan Tian) to emerge and **project out the eyes**. By doing this, and reflecting light back to the eye, awareness is born. Since light is an electric circuit, and not a particle, then the source-load relationship of the object of sense awarenesses (gunas and skandhas⁵⁶) then can actually drain the person. This is the assertion of the Taoist texts (multiple): that the five sense organs drain the person, especially obsessions of flavor (the tongue is the “fruit of the heart”) and music, which alters the hearts’ rhythms. So, perhaps Confucius wasn’t just an ultra-right-wing fuddy-duddy.

The Definition of a Sage, according to the “Nei Yeh” (Original Tao)

There are many things the Nei Yeh has to say about this issue, and we cannot copy the entire 26-verse text here⁵⁷. Besides, the poignant quotes have been compiled elsewhere, and the reader can read them from the footnotes⁵⁸ (and buy the book). The key points are these:

- ❖ Cleanse the chest
- ❖ Store the Qi or life force and vapors in the chest
- ❖ The sage will not befall Heavenly Disasters (chaos, etc.), animals’ claws, and human weapons.
- ❖ The sage will be at ease wherever he is/goes.
- ❖ The sage who has the Te has the Tao
- ❖ He who has the Tao flourishes, and he (or whatsoever) who doesn’t, perishes.

The Mysterious Pass, and the Soul Atom (Black Pearl)

The pursuit of the Golden Flower, and pushing past the Light, leads to the Void of darkness - Shunyata (Anutta) or Wuji. When that happens, they encounter the “black pearl hanging in the void of space”⁵⁹ and the author thinks this is **not** the Singularity, but is the mind’s impression of the soul; aka soul atom.

In a related subject, the Taoists asked where the “Mysterious Pass”⁶⁰ - that which makes us move without thinking - would be if a) it is not found inside the head, but b) also is not found outside the body, either.

Microcosm and Macrocosm

“As Above so Below” is an important alchemical maxim⁶¹. Turning “lead into gold” is a euphemism, and the “Sorcerer’s Stone” is nothing other than a lump of energy collected in the Dan Tians - particularly the lower - to have power and “spiritual immortality.”⁶² It’s also called a “spiritual embryo”⁶³ etc. But the key issue is the fractal aspect of all parts of the Universe. In fact, self-similarity is what is important, and is reflective of the ideology of all of these systems. Jesus makes frequent mention of the Kingdom, but in particular how it is neither in the sky nor the sea or Earth, and that it is “like a tiny mustard seed.”⁶⁴ These alchemical abstrusisms are *Taoish* at the minimum, and overtly Asiatic and mystical, at the very most likely.

⁵⁶ MIMS 2.10.1-.3 - MESS0025: Investigation - Sir Arthur's Gift

⁵⁷ Nei Yeh Quotes

⁵⁸ Nei Yeh - Internal Cultivation aka The Original Tao

⁵⁹ Chin-tan Ssu-pai-tzu Four Hundred 400 Words on the Golden Elixir.pdf

⁶⁰ NeichingTu.pdf

⁶¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/As_above_so_below

⁶² Hui-ming Ching Scripture of Wisdom and Life.pdf

⁶³ T'ai-hsi Ching Scripture of the Embryo Breathing.pdf

⁶⁴ Matthew 13:31

The Sacred Jewel

However, the most sacred jewel, in Taoist Alchemy at least, is not this stone or the “transmuted lead”⁶⁵. It is Xingming⁶⁶ - Life & Destiny - which are bright and transmutative. All life phenomena are ephemeral, and this is due to the fluid nature of the Changes and of the AME. But consider, also, that the Ming is tied to the Golden Flower, to the Qi-charge - and to karma. All of these things are overlapping, via the PEMF - the *F* power, which flowed out of the *L* power - and at the *heart* of It All is: GOD (I.A.O.) /| (G power). The knowledge of all of this is not important, however. Leastways not here. What is important is the freeing - on a quantum and psychic or even soul level - of the Self via these techniques. However, therein lies the worry for the wise and ancient Hindu (and Buddhists). “With power comes great responsibility,” and that is *not* liberating. So the Buddha - Shakyamuni Thus Come One - saw through all of this. For he was also tested by Mara (the “Devil”), 600 years earlier than Yeshua. He was able to escape the shackles, and become THE Buddha.

Enlightenment

The case *for* enlightenment was made much prior to Gautama Buddha. Buddha is an appellation, not a name. Yet it became his name. He was not the first or only one in search of nirvana and bodhi. But he was prophesied to be a success at this pursuit. He was, after a particularly difficult attempt, where he nearly killed himself in yogic practices (becoming a ‘baba’). When he heard from a music teacher, “If the string is too loose it will not play, if it is too tight it will snap.” He was enlightened. He left the group of friends that were in a similar pursuit and began his journey thinking through the Middle Way⁶⁷ (Tao). When he was enlightened, he gave a lecture to his friends on the Noble Eightfold Path⁶⁸ (Tao) and the Four Noble Truths⁶⁹. These numbers are not a surprise, they are of course Saturnian in their origin. Buddha wanted to tie his work back to the most ancient of the Rig Veda sources.

When he went forth from there, for sixty years of teaching, he began to logically lay out how the mind, reality, and issues of the spirit, of soul, really are. Contrary to belief the Buddha did not categorically deny the spirit, Devil, soul, or God. He did, however, critique them, and point out that all of these things are emanations, if not manifestations, of the mind; which is what the Taoists call “The Essential.” What is essential, is that the mind cognizes facts and is deluded by fiction. The war between these is ultimately at the root of good vs. evil. But this is pointless semantics. Instead, we are interested in the awareness - the golden light and electric connection (connected to the Lord and ‘consciousness’ in the “Big G” diagram) - which underpins the facts of observation, empiricism, investigation, and ultimately: gnosis.

There is no gnosis without logos. There are no logos without God; it is literally the Word of God. Therefore the issue of enlightenment *is* a matter of God. Why? Because to be enlightened may be a matter of gnosis, of bodhi, and a state of mind that enters “wuwei” (non-action), but it is also a matter of having the Right Knowledge; the true picture. The “Big G” is that picture⁷⁰... both connected to the ancients and the modern observations of Jupiter, and to the electric Force via Birkeland Currents, and to the 8 laws of physics, as well as the maths of the Fibonacci and phi. Golden ratios within golden ratios.

⁶⁵ ■ Lung-hu Ching Scripture of the Dragon and Tiger.pdf

⁶⁶ ■ Annotated-Translation-of-Innate Disposition and Lifepsan Xing-Ming-Gui-Zhi-Daniel-Burton-Rose.pdf

⁶⁷ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Middle-Way>

⁶⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Noble_Eightfold_Path

⁶⁹ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Four-Noble-Truths>

⁷⁰ ■ MIMS 1.12 - Self consistency of the Big G

The Bejeweled Diamond Net - Nested Fractals

Fractals were proposed long before Mandelbrot. The net is not a real net, it is a proposition. Within the net are diamonds, at each knot. And every facet of these diamonds reflects all the other diamonds both in form and varying sizes. This is a **perfect** reflection of the PEM theory of the F power⁷¹. Next, we must consider whether or not these reflections reflect the actual facets of reality.

Samsara

One of the understandings that the Buddhists updated, for example, from the most ancient days is that of the three-dimensional world of suffering. The “threefold world” or as the Taoists called it the “World of Red Dust,” refers to more than the 3D, it refers to the binding metaphysical and spiritual forces that tie mankind to the catastrophic dangers - Heavenly Disasters - and to what we call reality. We used a virtual philosophical particle before, the realion, to collapse this samsara into a singular moment of time⁷². But is this realion the same, functionally, as the diamonds in the bejeweled net? Or are the diamonds mere selves? Or are selves and moments the same?

Nirvana, Parinirvana, Paramitas, Siddhis

The pursuit of an escape from samsara is called Nirvana, meaning a release. Parinirvana is obtained when one is in repose, considering Nirvana. The pursuit of this form of enlightenment yields a particular form of gnosis that is called ‘wisdoms’ - paramitas. The collection of paramitas, with Logos, with the use of Tao-te, of “Qi in the chest.” leads specifically to powers, aka siddhis. These siddhis are referred to in the Bible as ‘spiritual gifts’ or fruits of a certain tree. That tree is the Tree of Life, and that means the chakra-nadi system of meridians (CDN⁷³, primo-vasculature, etc.) which is known also in Qabalah as Jacob’s Ladder.

Anuttara-Samyak-Sambodhi

The pursuit of this Tree of Life is, according to Genesis, the root of *spiritual* immortality. The fruit of this pursuit, according to the Buddhists is the reaching of [seeing] emptiness of the threefold world, by reaching the “3 bodhi”:

1. That all is empty and non-form.
2. The Truth of Birthlessness - since God-mind (Atman) is the only reality.
3. That Buddhahood is reached via the Lotus Vehicle, which functionally is summed up by Jesus’ concept of “the fisher of men.”
 - a. le - Study, Practice, and Teach; that is to say (in Buddhist speak) the Arhats, Pratyekabuddhas, and Bodhisattvas→Mahasattvas

Buddha’s Three Treasures

The three treasures of the religion are the Buddha, the Samgha, and the Tripitaka (Pali Canon of scripture). Why is this? The nature of the Buddha is considered by the Mahayanans to be a matter not of personality, or of thinking itself, but of an AME subset where Buddhmind is a universal consciousness that is found even within the inanimate, let alone all Life - spiritual or living. In this way, the Buddha mind itself is

⁷¹ [Explication of the Big G](#)

⁷² [MIMS 2.21 - MESS0024: Engineering MIMS Philosophy into a Plug and Play Platform \(P7 Resolution\)](#)

⁷³

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

atomochemical; it is fundamentally physics. The “church” of this belief system becomes an externalized memory and body of the prophet themselves, in this case Buddha, and the Canon represents the collected body of the religion, of the past and future, as a chain of Causation.

The Breath or Wind of God

So what the exact relationship between the Chinese ‘school’ of Qi and of Tao is, is not clear. It is clear that the two streams of thought (as MIMS) merged sometime well before Laozi or Zhuangzi. But the word Tao is quite ancient. Looking at the Etymology for both, we might find some mimical connection that elucidates the Law of Causality, as the Chinese saw it. For they did not worry about Karma until the Buddhists arrived in the early Religious Period, but they obviously saw (as we see with the 5 Elements or Phases school) every chain of causation in terms of process flow.

This screenshot shows the etymology page for the character '道' (Tao) on the Hanziyuan website. It includes sections for Oracle characters (none found), Bronze characters (11), Seal characters (1), and Liushutong characters (41). The Liushutong section shows various historical forms of the character, including those with the '礻' (spirit) radical and the '辶' (movement) radical. The page also lists the main pronunciation as 'dào' and provides English senses like 'path, road, street, method, way'.

This screenshot shows the etymology page for the character '氣' (Qi) on the Hanziyuan website. It includes sections for Oracle characters (none found), Bronze characters (none found), Seal characters (1), and Liushutong characters (0). The Liushutong section shows the character '气' (Qì) in its simplified form. The page lists the main pronunciation as 'qì' and provides English senses like 'air, steam, vapor, breath'. It also includes a usage example: '空氣 kōng qì (air)'.

Figure 1 & 2 - etymologies for Tao and Qi, respectively; credit: <https://hanziyuan.net/>

As anyone can see the etymology for the traditional form of Qi (breath, vapors), is not very ancient, but goes back to the Han or Qin Dynasty or Spring & Autumn Period. That’s circa Confucianism and Taoism as a religion proper, in the Transition Period. However, what we see with Tao (click image to expand) is that a great number of plasmaglyphs referring to thunderbolts, Saturn⁷⁴, the Cosmic Egg motif, and the related two and three powers (brothers) archetypes appear throughout the Bronze and especially Liushutong characters. This explains why the word 道 appears in Confucian “Analects”⁷⁵ more times than even the Laozi (Tao-te-ching),

⁷⁴ The Saturn Myth
⁷⁵ <https://ctext.org/analects>

and in the Mozi⁷⁶ more than either! It was a concept of a path or motion along a path that existed already for thousands of years. So far, though, no Shang oracle bones are found, so it isn't clear if it goes back to the Tepe, Archaic or Megalithic Periods per se. Then again, those bones might simply be destroyed. But as of now, no direct causal membrane exists that ties these together, but we know eventually they become merged by the Nei Yeh and Daodejing, and somehow having Qi (in the chest) becomes associative with having Tao-te (pronounced dow-duhh).

The cross “X”, Plague, Destruction, and the Saturn-Lord

In our examination of the comparison of the Chinese and Coelbren runes, of which 8 or so had direct overlap as plasmaglyphic constructs, we identified that the cross or “X” symbol was tied to the winds of destruction vis-a-vis the plagues. Indeed the word for insects 虻 includes this glyph, which is like a truncated swastika. We see that these destructive forces, also, are connected to comets, but even more anciently to the Fertility God, Saturn (Huang Di). Could it be that the connection of these is that Venus emerged from Saturn (as the Nahuatl evidence suggests), and more importantly that Dr. Velikovsky was right? That not only water of Saturn's rings⁷⁷, but mana from heaven (as hydrocarbons → carbohydrates) fed the Hebrews, and this ties comet Venus (the golden calf or Innana) to the Saturnian fertility God? No conclusions as of yet, but more to explore.

Qi as Charge (Q)

In the Charge Distributive Network paper⁷⁸, which built conclusions and hypotheses upon the more solid findings of the Electric Fields in situ experiments, in the appendix it was noted that the winds as carriers of disease might not only have been about comet plagues and destruction⁷⁹. It might be that literally, the wind carries some form of charge - protonic dust? - which can obstruct the nerves and block the vital nerve pathways. In winter the author finds himself constantly removing obstructive wind “evils” and cold sweat from the nape of the neck and trapezoids, as well as “Qi washing”⁸⁰ the San Jiao 5 (master of Defense Qi) point with warm palms. Furthermore, there are flu seasons, which are accompanied by aches and neck pain, in the Fall. The author notes also that the classics are correct⁸¹, that when you build your Kidney Qi, eventually there is a ‘chasing’ of a wind-like substance out of the knuckles, and also out of the ears resulting in the sounds of a seashell. The many blocks of the body are covered elsewhere⁸², but these are all classically written about. As recently as this weekend the author noted, however, the possibility that charges are swept ahead of storms. He could sense them in the body, and in the behaviors of people around him. A simple test would be to examine the rate of car accidents and violent crimes just prior to the arrival of low-pressure systems (so-called “Earth spots” especially).

⁷⁶ <https://ctext.org/mozi>

⁷⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0019103518303580>

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328697566_Clinical_Electric_Field_Measurements_In_situ_pre_and_post_treatment_measurement_data_with_weather_and_space-weather_lunar_and_solar_data_with_self-reported_pain_and_significance_scales_in_three_phases

⁸⁰ Clap the hands together, rub them warm, then apply a palm to any region; in this case 2” superior to the dorsal portion of the wrist, between the radius and ulna.

⁸¹ ■ Unschuld, Huang-Di-Nei-Jing-Su-Wen vol1.pdf

⁸² https://www.academia.edu/49945612/Alchemical_Process pp. 188-189

Table of Labels for Qi

<i>Label</i>	<i>Culture or Language</i>	<i>Invented Circa?</i>
Qi (ch'i) - "vapors", breath, steam	Chinese 气	Spring & Autumn Period (early Transition Period)
Ka - life-force or soul	Egyptian 𓆎	Old Kingdom ⁸³ (Megalithic Period)
Prana ⁸⁴ - breath, life force, or vitality	Vedic/India प्राण	7th-9th century? Probably Archaic
Ru'ach ⁸⁵ - "breath of God"/"holy spirit"	Hebrew/Aramaic רוח	Genesis (probably late Megalithic)
Pneuma - wind, breath, or spirit	Greek πνεῦμα	Presocratics ⁸⁶
Ruh - "holy spirit" ⁸⁷	Arabic رُوح or الرُّوح	Quran - 7th century
Orgone ⁸⁸ - esoteric energy or life force	America	1930s - Wilhelm Reich

Conclusion

The conclusions the author has reached are not as important as those the reader has reached. In the parameterization of the "New Religion," we can only provide the details of what is purely legitimate in the Religious Period from the past ages.. The "True Religion" goes all the way back to the death of the star, but the fruits of the Transition Period are both more mystical, and yet still based on something *like* charge, or ætheric. Besides that, people have at least three paths - 3 Tao - that can help them overcome the "mortal coil" and samsaric suffering. Enlightenment and liberation, or the pursuit of those things, can help us overcome the life we endure; while salvation can help us to overcome the anxiety we have about what is to come after. In terms of the philosophæther, and of being *entheos*/enthusiastic ("God within"), we can go far into understanding these prophets, the Thus Come Ones, the Pure Ones, by understanding their mechanisms. By chasing wisdoms, powers, and meditations... these pure beings encouraged people to develop their personal power and spiritual freedom. In the end, they are supposedly able to overcome the Heavenly Disasters (CHAOS) of life, transmute karma, improve fortunes, stave off Fate, and achieve their Destiny (ming)⁸⁹. Doing so consummates life - xingming.⁹⁰

⁸³ https://www.academia.edu/75590220/Ba_Ka_and_Akh_Concepts_in_the_Old_Kingdom_Ancient_Egypt

⁸⁴ Again, not a coincidence it is a homophone for prajna - wisdom.

⁸⁴ <https://www.wisdomlib.org/definition/prana> "Prāṇā itself represents *prāṇa*, one of the five vital airs. They are presided over by the Bhairava Asitāṅga. Calanī is the fifth of the Eight Mahāmāṭṛs, residing within the Māṭṛcakra (third of the five *cakras*) and **represents wind.**"

⁸⁵ <https://www.hebrew-streams.org/works/spirit/ruachpneuma.html>

⁸⁶ "Pneuma, "air in motion, breath, wind", is equivalent in the [material monism](#) of [Anaximenes](#) to aer (ἀήρ, "air") as the element from which all else originated. This usage is the earliest extant occurrence of the term in philosophy. A quotation from Anaximenes observes that "just as our soul (psyche), being air (aer), holds us together, so do breath (pneuma) and air (aer) encompass the whole world." In this early usage, aer and pneuma are synonymous." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pneuma>

⁸⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/R%C5%AB%E1%B8%A5>

⁸⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Orgone>

⁸⁹ [MIMS - The Big G of 5 Forces](#)

⁹⁰ [Ming_in_Neidan-libre.pdf](#)

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